

IDEOLOGY AND ART OF WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE'S SONNETS

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Abstract: In Shakespeare's sonnets, the idea is concise, the image is compact and clear, created within a certain literary form is considered significant in literature. The theme of each Shakespeare's sonnet does not repeat each other and has its own charm. The variety of themes in Shakespeare's sonnets are discussed in this article.

Key words: Shakespeare, sonnet, idea, art, theme, person, image, dream, love, hope.

The world of themes in fiction knows no bounds. Fiction, as a product of thought, is equally useful for the education of humanity's children, regardless of nation or people. In contrast to the fact that the mature representatives of world literature live and work in any corner of the world, their spiritual heritage serves as an invaluable treasure for the happiness and prosperity of mankind.

It is known that William Shakespeare, recognised as one of the great writers of world tragedies, won a place in the hearts of readers with his lyrical works. The first example of the sonnet genre appeared in Italian literature. There are a number of opinions in theoretical literature about the genre features and characteristics of the sonnet. In sonnets, it is important that the thought is concise and the image is compact, clear, and formally created within a certain pattern. The theme of each sonnet does not repeat each other and is uniquely charming.

The themes of love and romance pervade the works of the English writer who lived and created in the 16th century, whether large or small in size, particularly the main part of his sonnets.

When describing the image of a woman, Shakespeare depicted her pure heart and pure desires artistically and with pleasure. Love is a cure for all pains; sometimes it brings joy to its owner, sometimes it tears hearts like a dagger. Even bitter things become sweet because of love. It is extremely delicate and sometimes harder than a rock. A woman is ready to give her whole being, even her life, for her family, spouse, and children. A lover who suffers from the pain of love understands the power of love. A lover does not want to lose his love. Because the expression of concepts such as woman and love, love and infatuation, love and loyalty, kindness and consequence, and courage and courage is a phenomenon that does not require religion, nation, or race, as well as international boundaries, distance, or proximity between eras.

A new day, a new life, a new dream are all precursors to a person's hopes. As if a person has just stepped into life, his heart is surrounded by priceless experiences. Even the things that he has seen for many years shine anew in his eyes on a new day. A person is a complex being; when he is in a good mood and his happiness is limitless, he enjoys existence and sees the world in a new light. In particular, if the heart is filled with love, it is even more wonderful and strange; it is a divine feeling. William Shakespeare expressed this aspect in the following way:

Every morning the sun is new and old,
My love is like the sun...

In these verses, the sun, which is visible every day, appears brighter and more attractive to the lover who is drunk with the wine of love. Shakespeare describes its brilliant, dazzling, and burning beauty as "my love is like the sun", a beautiful allegory. He expresses his desire through artistic depiction.

When you look at people's lives, you are sometimes surprised. Someone loves and enjoys spring, while someone despises it. Some poets connect autumn's abscission (the shedding of leaves) with the end of human life, others seek beauty from it. Someone associates the coldness of winter with the moments of bad luck in his life, while another person associates his beautiful life with sweet moments, enjoying the white snow of winter.

How like a winter hath my absence been
From thee, the pleasure of the fleeting year!
What freezings have I felt, what dark days seen!
What old December's bareness everywhere!

The season of spring is the symbol of awakening. In this season, new dreams and hopes sprout not only in nature, but also in our hearts and bodies. The beauty of spring encourages people to love, enjoy life and live with pleasure. It gives purity and goodness to hearts, brings love to people's hearts. In particular, the awakening of nature, the singing of birds, the sweet smell of flowers, raise the mood of people and provide spiritual nourishment. But sometimes even such a pleasant, natural situation cannot have its effect on a person. Because without a lover, no beauty can give pleasure to a lover.

From you have I been absent in the spring,
When proud-pied April, dressed in all his trim,
Hath put a spirit of youth in everything,
That heavy Saturn laughed and leaped with him.
Yet nor the lays of birds, nor the sweet smell
Of different flowers in odour and in hue,

Could make me any summer's story tell,
Or from their proud lap pluck them where they grew:
Nor did I wonder at the lily's white,
Nor praise the deep vermilion in the rose;
They were but sweet, but figures of delight
Drawn after you, – you pattern of all those.
Yet seem'd it winter still, and, you away,
As with your shadow I with these did play.

Nightingales begin to walk with the arrival of spring, and lovers express their love to their beloved. According to the poet, with the arrival of summer, even the nightingales stop singing their epic. But the warmth of summer has always brought purity to people's hearts.

The world of themes in fiction knows no bounds. Fiction, as a product of thought, serves the same purpose for the education of humanity's children, regardless of nation or people. Mature representatives of world literature serve humanity, regardless of where they live and work. We have often heard the instructive idea that light comes from the East. After all, the literature, art, and culture of the Eastern peoples could serve as a beacon for the Western Renaissance.

In conclusion, in William Shakespeare's work, various natural phenomena and events are described in harmony with the inner world, appearance, and mood of the lyrical hero. Secondly, the theme of love which is the focus of the artist's attention, gained a special appeal through beautiful allusions in the poet's poetry. The poet praised pure love and loyalty in his sonnets. Because it is on the basis of these that the next generation will be born, grow up and will be mature. Such a young generation will continue the work of their parents and contribute to the development of the country, the future of the nation, and world peace. Everyone sees their wishes and dreams in their child. All parents enjoy it and feel happy.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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